

From digestate and CO₂ to single-cell proteins: combined by-product valorization for circular carbon and nutrient utilization

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Abstract

This study explores the *hydrogenotrophic* production of valuable single-cell proteins (SCPs) based on the utilization of CO₂ from biogas upgrading and nutrients from digestate, by-product of anaerobic digestion (AD), thus contributing to meet the growing global protein demand in a circular way. Experiments conducted under both aerobic and anaerobic conditions, utilizing synthetic nutrients and CO₂, demonstrated faster microbial growth in aerobic conditions with cell doubling time of 15 ± 2 h in aerobic conditions against 44 ± 0.1 h in anaerobic conditions. After identifying the most productive microbial platform, experiments were conducted using CO₂ and nutrients from digestate, after a proper pre-treatment for pathogen removal. Overall, the results highlight the potential to produce SCPs from AD by-products, biomass production almost quadrupled and SCP/biomass ratio increasing by 19%, compared to the utilization of synthetic nutrient sources.

Keywords

Anaerobic digestion; carbon and nutrient upcycling; CO₂ utilization; digestate valorization; single-cell-proteins

INTRODUCTION

The global population is expected to reach 9.5 billion by 2050 (Henchion et al., 2017), rising protein demand and requiring a considerable expansion in land used for soybean cultivation and animal husbandry, which contributes to environmental degradation and rising agricultural waste (Matassa et al., 2015). These wastes are often processed through anaerobic digestion (AD), a sustainable waste-to-energy method, but requiring proper by-product disposal. Exploring alternative protein sources derived from AD by-products could represent a win-win solution, tackling multiple challenges simultaneously: pollution reduction, waste valorization, resource recovery, better satisfied global protein demand. Single-cell proteins (SCPs) are microbial cells rich in protein, which can be derived from yeast, bacteria, fungi, algae and used as food and feed supplements (Nasseri et al., 2011). SCPs can be produced by different raw materials.

AD is aimed at biogas (60% CH₄, 40% CO₂) production, which is typically valorised as energy source after upgrading process for CO₂ removal and dismissal. Digestate is an organic nutrient-rich AD by-product, traditionally used as fertilizer through direct application to farmland (Kovačić et al., 2022). Due to pollution concerns, the European Union strictly regulated its use, creating an urgent need for alternative valorization routes (Hermann et al., 2019). CO₂ from upgrading could be used as gaseous carbon source to support a bacteria-based autotrophic bioprocess aimed at SCP production while digestate could represent the nutrient source of the process. Therefore, *hydrogenotrophic route* (CO₂ and H₂ as carbon and energy sources) for SCP production emerged as profitable platform from previous economic assessment. In this research, the process was experimentally validated, comparing synthetic and digestate-derived nutrients in SCP production. To this purpose, an *aerobic isolate* and an *anaerobic consortium* were first cultivated in synthetic medium. Afterwards, the most productive platform was tested using nutrients from digestate and the results of both configurations compared. This innovative bioprocess offers a promising pathway towards achieving both food security and environmental sustainability, by turning waste into high-quality proteins.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Laboratory validation: experimental set-up

An *aerobic hydrogenotrophic isolate* and an *anaerobic acetogenic consortium* were selected for laboratory validation based on H₂ and CO₂ consumption. The *anaerobic consortium* was intended to

produce SCP in a two-step process: first, it would convert CO₂ and hydrogen to acetate, which would then serve as carbon substrate for a second bioreactor, where an acetate-consuming pure strain could grow and efficiently produce proteins. In contrast, the *aerobic isolate* was expected to directly produce protein from gas fermentation in a single-step process.

The experimental validation was divided into two main Test Series (Figure 1). Test Series 1 was carried out using synthetic mineral medium, CO₂, H₂ and air (aerobic condition) and CO₂, H₂ (anaerobic condition), according to Table 1. The aim was to compare the performance of the *aerobic isolate* and the *anaerobic consortium* based on cell doubling time, maximum biomass and protein production. The microbial platform showing the fastest growth in Test Series 1 was then selected for Test Series 2, where synthetic mineral medium was replaced with nutrients from liquid digestate. All experiments were carried out in duplicate with abiotic negative control.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the experimental design

In **Test Series 1**, 1-L batch bioreactors were operated, maintaining a liquid-gas ratio of 25-75% (gas phase compositions are shown in Table 1) at 200 rpm, and pH 7. The reactors were inoculated with 5% v/v of biomass. The *aerobic isolate* was grown at 25 °C, while the *anaerobic consortium* was cultivated at optimal temperature of 37 °C. Gas and liquid samples were collected daily to assess gas consumption, pH, biomass and protein production.

Table 1. Gas phase composition (% v/v) in aerobic and anaerobic experiments

Condition	CO ₂	H ₂	O ₂	N ₂
Aerobic	10	40	10	40
Anaerobic	20	80	< 2	< 2

In **Test Series 2**, 2-L semi-continuous gas-tight bioreactors in aerobic conditions containing 250 mL of pre-treated digestate were prepared. The reactors were inoculated with 5% v/v aerobic biomass and incubated at 25°C at 200 rpm, and pH 7. Gas and liquid samples were collected daily to assess gas consumption, pH, biomass and protein production according to analytical methods described below.

In both series, the concentration of dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) and dissolved organic carbon (DOC), and total nitrogen content were measured to compute the carbon and nitrogen balance.

Digestate pre-treatment

Before using digestate in Test Series 2, a preliminary characterization campaign on digestate has been done, to verify the theoretical nutrient content. To remove pathogens and heavy metals, a combination of technologies has been studied and tested, involving centrifugation, filtration and coagulant dosage

optimization via Jar Tests (ASTM D2035-08). For phosphate supplementation, 1 g·L⁻¹ of KH₂PO₄ was added to pre-treated digestate. A final step of autoclavation and pH adjustment to 7 using HCl.

Analytical methods

CO₂ and H₂ consumption were measured with an Agilent 7890A GC-TCD (Agilent technologies, USA). For biomass determination, optical absorbance at 600 nm was measured using a SPECTROstar Nano at 600 nm (BMG LABTECH, Germany). Dry biomass concentration was calculated as total suspended solids according to Standard Methods. The protein concentration was determined using a BCA Protein Assay Kit and absorbance was measured at 562 nm using a spectrophotometer SPECTROstar Nano (BMG LABTECH, Germany). Liquid digestate characterization was carried out through conventional methods for total nitrogen, ammonium, Total and Volatile Solids (TS, VS) and phosphorus determination. Metal content (Al, As, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, Zn, Mo) was determined through Atomic Spectroscopy ICP-MS; pathogens (*Escherichia coli*, *Clostridium perfringens*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella* spp. and *Campylobacter* spp.) were analysed through plate count and immunofluorescence. DIC, DOC, and total nitrogen content were assessed through TOC-VCSH (Shimadzu, Japan) analyser on 0.22 µm membrane filtered samples and pH adjusted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results in **Test Series 1** (Table 2) showed that both, the *aerobic isolate* and the *anaerobic consortium* were able to grow using synthetic mineral medium and CO₂ as carbon source. While the *aerobic isolate* was able to grow at 25 °C, avoiding external heating, the *anaerobic consortium* was only able to grow at 37 °C (data not shown). Since the *anaerobic consortium* exhibited significantly slower growth compared to the *aerobic isolate*, it was discarded for Test Series 2, based on digestate nutrient utilization in single-step process.

Table 2. Cell doubling time for *aerobic isolate* and *anaerobic consortium* with synthetic nutrients

Microbial platform	Condition	Doubling time (h)	Lag phase (h)
Aerobic isolate	H ₂ -CO ₂ /AIR	15 ± 2	48
Anerobic consortium	H ₂ -CO ₂	44 ± 0.1	96

Digestate characterization revealed that the pre-treatment did not significantly affect the nutrient content (Table 3); however, it effectively removed *Clostridium perfringens* spores, reducing them to <10 CFU. Metal levels were already below legal limits.

Table 3. Original and pre-treated liquid digestate: nutrient content comparison

Sample	Ammonium (gN/L)	Total Nitrogen (gN/L)	COD (gO ₂ /L)	Phosphate (mg/L)
Original LD	0.91	1.02	1.37	UDL
Pre-treated LD	0.86	0.89	0.98	UDL

UDL= under detection limit

The comparison between results from **Test Series 1 and 2** (Table 4) shows that the maximum biomass almost quadrupled when using nutrient from pre-treated digestate compared to that produced with synthetic nutrients, while SCP-biomass ratio reached 75%, reflecting a 19% increase compared to synthetic nutrients. Moreover, over time, the SCP/biomass ratio increased from 15 to 75% (Figure 2), reaching a biomass concentration of almost 1 g·L⁻¹ as DM, thus providing promising prospects for future continuous implementation.

Table 4. Results of *aerobic isolate* using CO₂-H₂ but different nutrient source: synthetic nutrients (Test Series 1) and nutrients from digestate (Test Series 2)

Nutrient source	Maximum biomass (mg/L)	SCP/biomass (%)
Synthetic (Test Series 1)	254 ± 22	63 ± 4
Digestate (Test Series 2)	966 ± 16	75 ± 3

Figure 2. Trend in SCP and biomass ratio during Test Series 2.

In conclusion, the nutrient content in digestate makes it an ideal feedstock for microbial growth, while CO₂ represents a cost-free carbon source to support the autotrophic production of SCPs in a resource-efficient manner. The bioconversion of AD by-products into valuable proteins not only addresses the disposal challenges associated with anaerobic digestion but also contributes to meeting the growing global protein demand in a sustainable way.

Acknowledgments

PID2022-139110OA-I00 project CIRCULARBIOMED
A2A Life Company

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